

Characterization of Biodegradable Polycaprolactone Containing Titanium Dioxide Micro and Nanoparticles

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Abstract : Composites based on a biodegradable polycaprolactone (PCL) containing 0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 wt % of titanium dioxide (TiO₂) micro and nanoparticles were prepared by melt mixing and the effect of filler type and contents on the thermal properties, dynamic-mechanical behaviour and morphology were investigated. Measurements of storage modulus and loss modulus by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) showed better results for microfilled PCL/TiO₂ composites than nanofilled composites, with the same filler content. DSC analysis showed that the T_g and T_c of micro and nanocomposites were slightly lower than those of neat PCL. The crystallinity of the PCL increased with the addition of TiO₂ micro and nanoparticles; however, the ρ_c for the PCL was unchanged with micro TiO₂ content. The thermal stability of PCL/TiO₂ composites were characterized using thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). The initial weight loss (5 wt %) occurs at slightly higher temperature with micro and nano TiO₂ addition and with increasing TiO₂ content.

Keywords : polycaprolactone, titanium dioxide, thermal properties, morphology

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